

Research Article

Academic Achievement in EFL Learners: The Role of Emo-sensory Intelligence, L2 Ego, and Class Attendance

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ABSTRACT

Introduction: Although psychological and affective variables are known to influence second language learning, limited research has examined the predictive role of emo-sensory intelligence, L2 ego, and willingness to attend class in the academic achievement of intermediate EFL learners.

Purpose: This study aimed to investigate these associations and explore students' perceptions of how these factors affect their academic performance

Methodology: The study followed an explanatory sequential mixed-methods design. In the quantitative phase, 206 university-level EFL learners were selected through convenience sampling. Participants completed three validated instruments assessing emo-sensory intelligence, L2 ego, and willingness to attend class. In the qualitative phase, six students were purposively sampled for semi-structured interviews to gain deeper insight into their academic experiences. Quantitative data were analyzed using Pearson product-moment correlation and multiple regression analysis to examine relationships and predictive power. Qualitative data were coded thematically, and inter-coder reliability was calculated to ensure consistency in theme identification.

Results: Pearson correlation analyses revealed significant positive relationships among all three psychological constructs and academic achievement. Multiple regression analysis identified willingness to attend class as the strongest predictor of academic performance. Thematic analysis of interview data, supported by high inter-coder reliability, yielded seven recurrent themes: emotional challenges, instructional methods, sensory appreciation, emotional feedback, classroom attractiveness, learner energy, and stress.

Conclusion: Findings highlighted the importance of psychological engagement and emotional resonance in language learning. This study sheds new light on how psychological traits including emotional and neurological support from teachers in the classroom impacts student engagement and learning.

1. Introduction

In general, intelligence is defined as “an individual’s cognitive ability, focusing on logical reasoning, solving problems, and thinking in abstract ways” (Pishghadam et al., 2020, p. 176). The background witnesses a shift in attention towards intelligence, transmitting from intelligence quotient (IQ) (Galton, 1879) to Emotional Intelligence (EI) (Bar-On, 1988). As Galton (1879) pinpointed,

Psychometric intelligence concentrated on cognitive abilities that are germane to academic success, representing that learners who are possessing higher IQs tended to perform more successfully in school settings. Although Goleman (1995) maintained that EQ holds more importance than IQ as it impacts cognitive abilities and behavior, studies on EI reveal various meanings, involving diverse non-cognitive

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skills that can enhance learning capabilities. Later, Lombard (2007) suggested the notion of sensory intelligence to emphasize the contribution of senses by individuals which led to the concept of Sensory Quotient (SQ), implying the direct attention to the basic sensory wiring of our brain, which dominates IQ and EQ. In this line, Pishghadam et al. (2020) developed the concept of emo-sensory intelligence (ESI), defined as the mental awareness of emotions, elicited by sensory inputs, to make a compromise between SQ and EQ. ESI is indeed related to other psychological attributes such as identity and willingness to communicate in learning a new language. While SI emphasizes sensations and EI is rooted in emotions, the ESI highlights the interconnectedness of sensations and emotions, contrasting the two and uncovering hidden intelligence (Mohammadi & Modarresi, 2023). ESI is rooted in the literature of Emotionality (Emotion + Frequency), treating emotions elicited by sensory stimuli as a response to emotions induced by sensory inputs (Pishghadam, 2015). Accordingly, a significant body of literature has examined the potential impact of ESI on second language acquisition research including identity and L2 ego (Kaly & Heesacker, 2003).

Indeed, several authors have delved into the concepts of identity and ego with respect to the learning and teaching of English language (Dörnyei, 2005; Norton, 1997). In the same vein, a number of researchers have displayed an increasing fascination with the effectiveness of language ego as a serious obstacle to acquiring a second language (Ehrman, 1993; Razmjoo & Neissi, 2010). To be more specific, the concept of language ego was, initially, suggested by Guiora et al. (1972) to establish a rationale for the identity a person shapes based on the specific language they use. Meanwhile, Ehrman (1999) highlights how important language ego is in researching learners with varying levels of ego boundaries, such as thin (permeable) and thick (not as permeable) boundaries. Brown (2014) declares, "The openness, vulnerability, and ambiguity tolerance of those with thin ego boundaries create different pathways to success from those with hard-driving, systematic, perfectionist thick ego boundaries" (p. 159). Undoubtedly, L2 learners who are able to handle their unconscious ego-defense seem to be more willing to cope with difficult tasks (Bainbridge & Del Negro, 2020). Indeed, it seems that L2 ego is related to students' willingness to participate in doing the learning tasks.

Class attendance (CA) serves as an indispensable part of learning (Gump, 2004), and since the opportunity to practice the language outside the classroom is not considerate, CA becomes more crucial for attaining proficiency in a foreign language. Furthermore, several studies (e.g., Gump, 2005) have

confirmed a reverse association between absences and final grades. Meanwhile, research into CA has focused on other variables like workload, tedious lectures, health issues, and conflicts with social activities (Van Blerkom, 1992), and more importantly, on determinants of CA, e.g., motivation, prior GPA, self-financing by students, hours worked on jobs, quality of teaching, and nature of the class (Devadoss & Foltz, 1996). However, other important factors such as emotions and senses could equally contribute to this literature.

Nevertheless, relatively little research has been carried out on the relation between language ego and emo-sensory intelligence in the educational setting (Pishghadam et al., 2020). Furthermore, learning a language occurs within an interactive setting (Jalilzadeh et al., 2022), and effective language learning relies on participation and communication in the classroom (Allwright, 1984).

Indeed, the classroom setting allows for an efficient way for language learners, especially those learning English as a foreign language, to communicate and interact with each other. Hence, EFL students are expected to attend classes to engage in direct language interaction and receive feedback to enhance their educational progress (Rouhani & Modarresi, 2023). As of the significance of CA in EFL contexts, absenteeism still seems to be a major concern in some educational systems. The current importance is that academic success is an important factor that can be improved while in school. The idea of using supportive interventions to teach English has been proposed, with the aim of showing which of these psychological factors are more effective in terms of language skills (Mehrani Rad et al., 2018). ESI can further prepare students to develop learning through language skills. In this way, students are able to identify the values and beliefs contained in the sensory and emotional elements, and use them to generate and develop ideas for speaking and visual activities, enabling them to develop a variety of Able to hear and speak from cultures and recognize similarities and differences between them.

The current literature represents the effect of emotional factors on learning and teaching processes (Khajavy et al., 2025; Rahimi & Modarresi, 2023; Salovey & Mayer, 1990) highlighted the role of emotional intelligence in monitoring one's own and others' emotions and guiding thinking and actions. Intelligence is believed to have various aspects (Li & Schmiedek, 2001), prompting early researchers to go beyond cognitive skills and examine additional abilities (Cherniss, 2004). For instance, for Thorndike (1920), social intelligence was the extent to which one could effectively understand and manage interpersonal interactions. Similarly, Gardner (1983) introduced the concept of multiple intelligences,

including interpersonal intelligence along with other cognitive-based intelligences. Likewise, Sternberg (1985) added practical intelligence, maintaining that interpersonal, intrapersonal, and practical intelligences are essential for successful modifications in life. Bar-On (1988) coined the term EQ as a complement to IQ, defining it as an amalgamation of vital social and emotional skills needed for navigating the challenges of daily life. The idea of emotional intelligence silenced the loud discrepancies between logic and feelings (Matthews et al., 2003), and attracted extensive attention since its very inception, and became a topic of wide resonance (Matthews et al., 2003). Its popularity highly traces back to Goleman's (1995) EI that introduced the idea to the public.

Although the concept of language identity has been meticulously studied across different disciplines like the traditional psychoanalytical school and educational research (Ehrman, 1998), the literature on language ego in the field of SLA is rare (Brown, 2014; Guiora, 1994; Schwartz et al., 2000). In their seminal work, Guiora et al. (1972) proposed the notion of language ego to connote the identity that an individual forms in relation to their spoken language. Whereas many factors were discovered through the thorough analysis of language ego (Schwartz et al., 2000), some researchers explored innovative strategies to address ego of L2 learners (e.g., Peirce, 1995; Spielmann & Radnofsky, 2001). For Pierce (1995), Learners may encounter ego conflict when interacting with people from different cultural backgrounds. In the same vein, Philips (1991) stated that a positive language ego is beneficial for students in reducing anxiety and overcoming inhibition in the stressful environment of learning a second language. In this regard, Tavakkoli et al. (2014) investigated the role of different ego types in enhancing language skills for English as a Foreign Language (EFL) students and concluded that students with achieved ego types outperformed those with foreclosed and diffused ego types. Much of the existing literature on language ego has addressed the association of ego development with cognitive factors and personality traits whereas other significant factors like environmental influences have been underrated in the previous research works (Winnicott, 1991).

While researchers such as Gump (2004) and Cross, et al. (1993) questioned the significance of CA as the best possible predictor of student achievement, He (2015) considers CA as the easiest factor that is under students' control. Similarly, Credé et al. (2010) found that CA contributes to college grade more than any other factors like standardized admission tests, high school GPA, study habits, and study skills. Additionally, Clump et al. (2003) examined the

impact of CA in a general psychology course and found that CA is conducive to academic achievement even if the information presented in the classroom are available for the students who fail to attend the class. In this respect, McCroskey and his colleagues who developed the idea of WTC with respect to native language communication (McCroskey, 1992; McCroskey & Richmond, 1990) contended that while environmental circumstances may influence one's inclination to communicate, people have similar WTC tendencies in different settings. Moreover, they found that different factors could predict WTC such as self-esteem, introversion, communication ability, and cultural diversity.

However, certain crucial elements have been disregarded in relation to communication abilities (Modarresi, 2009). For instance, factors linked to practical knowledge and various sensory encounters may impact communication among learners in various ways. There has been a lot of discussion in the field of education regarding the concept of ego, including its theoretical significance, its measurement, and its potential benefits. Certainly, with the focus on L2 ego in the field of SLA, it is essential to carefully analyze this concept and its possibilities. Furthermore, unlike the works carried out in the literature on students' motivation (see Dörnyei, 2001), research into willingness to attend class has been underestimated in the field. Works on class attendance are not only linked to students' success but also connected to other key factors in the language education agenda, such as L2 ego. Despite heated debate over its suitability and efficiency, English has been incorporated into Iranian educational institutions as the primary global language.

Point taken, the researchers posed the following three research questions in order to carry out the study:

1) *Is there any significant relationship between emo-sensory intelligence, L2 ego, and willingness to attend class with students' academic achievement for EFL intermediate students?*

2) *Do emo-sensory intelligence, L2 ego, and willingness to attend class predict academic achievement for EFL intermediate students?*

3) *What do the students think about the role of emo-sensory intelligence, L2 ego, willingness to attend class in improving learning success?*

2. Methodology

The current research employed an explanatory sequential mixed-methods design (Johnson & Christensen, 2012), beginning with a quantitative approach, using a correlational design which

identified the relationships between the four main variables of the study (emo-sensory intelligence, L2 ego, willingness to attend class, and students' academic achievement), and supplemented by interview methods to increase the internal validity of the findings (Dörnyei, 2007).

2.1. Participants

At first, a total number of 254 English-major university students (females: $n=157$, 61.8%; males: $n=97$, 38.2%; Mean age=20.45 SD=2.14) participated in the study from Islamic Azad University of Quchan, Islamic Azad University of Mashhad, Tabaran University of Mashhad, Ferdowsi University of Mashhad, Imam Reza University of Mashhad, and Islamic Azad University of Neyshabor, located in the northeast of Iran, selected based on convenience sampling. The study included 442 students, and 254 participants were chosen using Krejcie and Morgan's (1970) sample size table with a 99% confidence level and 0.05 error rate for a small population. Students participated in this study had already successfully completed their four-credit English courses in English Structure and English Conversation. Both male and female students, including both junior and senior levels, were present in this work. Nevertheless, the students became homogeneous in terms of overall language knowledge by their performance on the Oxford Placement Test. To ensure the homogeneity of the students, only students with intermediate scores (30-44) on the OPT test were included in the study. In so doing, some participants were excluded from the study since their scores on this test were not at the intermediate level. Out of 254 participants, students remained to participate in this study was 206 (females: $n=129$, 62.6%; males: $n=77$, 37.4%; Mean age=20.67, SD=2.14). In addition, six students (females: $n=4$, 66.7%; males: $n=2$, 33.3%; Mean age=20.33; SD=2.09) were selected to participate in the qualitative phase of the study based on purposive sampling. The data were collected until no new information was added. The sample size seemed to be adequate since, according to Dörnyei (2007), an interview study with a sample size of six to 10 might work well.

2.2. Instruments

The first instrument employed to evaluate the language skills of second language learners was the OPT, a proficiency assessment containing 60 multiple-choice questions on vocabulary and grammar. The evaluation standards classify test takers into four English proficiency levels: elementary (1-14), pre-intermediate (15-29), intermediate (30-44), and upper-intermediate (45-50) (UCLES, 2001). Those volunteers identified at the intermediate level were part of the current study.

To measure emo-sensory intelligence, ESI scale

was employed, designed by Pishghadam et al. (2020) in the Persian language. It comprises 144 five-point Likert-type items, entailing all the conventionally acknowledged senses of hearing, sight, touch, movement, taste, and smell. The results of CFA specified six models for the six senses, each including 24 items with 4 latent variables, namely recognition, labeling, monitoring, and management.

To assess students' L2 ego, the questionnaire of L2 Ego for Iranian EFL learners was utilized, developed and validated by Farsad and Modarresi (2023). The questionnaire included 16 items using a 5-point Likert scale, ranging from strongly disagree to strongly agree. The questionnaire's reliability was assessed at 0.80 through Cronbach's Alpha.

To examine the reasons for students' CA, the Willingness to Attend Class (WTAC) Questionnaire was utilized, which was designed by Rajabnejad et al. (2017). It includes 25 five-point Likert scale items, ranging from strongly disagree (1) to strongly agree (5). These items relate to the five key components that make up the scale: Teacher knowledge (TK), Teacher methodology (TM), Teacher care (TC), Teacher characteristics (TCH), and Teacher environment (TE).

To examine students' responses to the role of emo-sensory intelligence, L2 ego, and willingness to attend class in improving learning success, the researchers constructed semi-structured interview questions. Two English teaching experts who had been teaching at Islam Azad University in Quchan verified the accuracy of the questions' content. After experts provide feedback, the researchers verified the questions' validity.

2.3. Data collection

Data were collected from 206 English as a Foreign Language (EFL) student over a period of seven weeks. The researchers attempted to utilize more samples as correlational studies require a sufficient number of participants to generalize the results (Dörnyei, 2007). During the first week, they distributed OPT to the participants. During the second week, they distributed emo-sensory questionnaire to the students and they were instructed on how to respond to the item and the allotted time. During the third week, the researchers administered L2 ego questionnaire to the learners and they received guidance on how to respond to the items in due time.

During the fourth week, the students were given the questionnaire of willingness to attend class, and they were provided feedback on how to respond to the items as well as the time allotted for

it. As for the students' academic achievement, the teacher considered their total average score. During the fifth and sixth weeks, the aim was to collect the feedback of the interviewees regarding their perceptions towards the role of emo-sensory intelligence, L2 ego, and willingness to attend class in improving learning success. They wrote the questions in English and the students were required to reply to the questions precisely. The researchers using content analysis held interview sessions with six participants based on the data saturation method to find out in-depth information. After transcription of the interviews, the researchers read them several times, highlighting and annotating major common themes. Initially, they asked the participants to introduce themselves. They were allowed to respond to the questions either in English language or Persian language.

To address the first research question, the Pearson moment-to-moment correlation coefficient was run to specify the significant relationship of emo-sensory intelligence, L2 ego, and willingness to attend class with students' achievement for EFL students. To address the second research question regarding the extent to which emo-sensory intelligence, L2 ego, and willingness to attend class could predict academic achievement for EFL students, multiple regression was performed. To answer the last research question regarding the students' thoughts about the role of emo-sensory intelligence, L2 ego, and willingness to attend class in their academic achievement, they used theme-based categorization to analyze the data.

3. Results

3.1. Emo-sensory intelligence, L2 Ego, willingness to attend class, and students' academic achievement

As of the significant association of emo-sensory intelligence, L2 ego, and willingness to attend class with students' academic achievement for EFL intermediate students, descriptive statistics and Pearson correlation coefficient were run to achieve the first objective of the study. Prior to performing the formula, they initially assessed the normality assumptions for the scores. The initial step involved verifying that the skewness and kurtosis fell within the anticipated range of +2 to -2. Descriptive analyses revealed the mean and standard deviation scores for three variables related to emo-sensory intelligence, L2 ego, willingness to attend class, and students' academic achievement, respectively: $M=489.79$; $SD=58.19$; $M=48.60$; $SD=6.62$; $M=82.16$, $SD=9.20$; and $M=15.16$, $SD=2.0$.

Table 1.

Correlations between the Variables

		Academic Achievement
Emo-sensory Intelligence	Pearson Correlation	.50**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.00
	N	206
L2 Ego	Pearson Correlation	.68**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.00
	N	206
Willingness to Attend Class	Pearson Correlation	.71**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.00
	N	206

** Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

As displayed by Table 1, the results obtained from Pearson product-moment correlation coefficient showed that there was a large, positive correlation between emo-sensory intelligence, L2 ego, and willingness to attend class with students' academic achievement for EFL students [$r=.50, .68, .71, n=206, p<.05$], with higher scores on emo-sensory intelligence, L2 ego, willingness to attend class associated with higher academic achievement for EFL students' scores, based on the guideline proposed by Cohen (1992).

3.2. The Predictor of Academic Achievement in ESI, L2 Ego, and Willingness to Attend Class

The second objective of the research dealt with the predictors of academic achievement in emo-sensory intelligence, L2 ego, willingness to attend class components. In doing so, the following statistical analyses were performed. As of the first step, the researchers ensured that the independent variables did not have a too-close connection (a condition known as Multicollinearity). There is some connection between the dependent and model variables. In addition, there was no breach of the multicollinearity condition because the tolerance value for each independent variable was more than .10. The VIF value, which was within the threshold of 10, provided further confirmation of this. There was thus no violation of data. The Mahalanobis distance was also inspected to see if there were any outliers. Since there were three independent variables in this research, the critical value was 14.35 which was not higher than 16.27, according to the recommendations of Tabachnick and Fidell (2001). Model Summary's output also showed that the value was 0.51. That is, the model that illustrated scores on conceptions of intelligence and teaching motivation could account for 51% of the variation in academic achievement scores when presented as a percentage. Next, the ANOVA Test was performed to measure the statistical significance of the results which tested the hypothesis that multiple R in the population equals

zero (0). The model reached statistical significance ($F=70.16$, $Sig = .00$, $p<.05$).

Table 2.

The Predictors of Academic Achievement in Emo-sensory Intelligence, L2 ego, Willingness to ATTEND CLASS

Model	Standardized	t	Sig.
	Coefficients Beta		
	(Constant)	1.52	.12
1	Emo-sensory Intelligence	.04	.66
	L2 Ego	-.04	-.23
	Willingness to Attend Class	.72	3.61
			.81

As indicated in Table 2, in order to determine which variables in the model impacted the prediction of the dependent variable, examining the Beta column revealed that the highest beta coefficient was .72 for the willingness to attend class. This indicates that this variable provided the greatest impact in elucidating students' academic success when the variation accounted for by all other variables in the model was held constant. The Beta values for other variables were not significant since the significant value for each of them was more than .05, so they did not significantly contribute to the prediction of academic achievement.

3.3. Results from Students' Responses to the Interviews

As for the last research question of the study regarding the students' thought about the role of emo-sensory intelligence, L2 ego, willingness to attend class in improving learning success, the common themes elicited from the interviews are reported as follows. One of the students said:

In the proceeding terms, I had some psychological attributes that were agenzizing for me because I saw myself unable to participate in class discussions and I had less self-esteem and I was suffering from shyness; however, I had a different teacher during last term since he was encouraging and positive. He pushed me to participate in class discussions and called me by my name and was emotionally supportive. This sort of behavior helped me much to fortify my English language and promote my learning development.

It seems that teachers who are more motivated and have a good vibe for teaching English language are more attractive to the students and devote enough time to work with the students and to examine their assignments. Teachers should attract the students to be present in class since this would have a negative effect too. One of the students stated:

My English teacher is attractive and he tries to teach the lessons energetically and he works well in the class and he is on the board most of the time, she and

his class are interesting to me and she does not transfer her sadness or anxiety to us.

Students indicated that significant factors linked to L2 ego play crucial roles in effectively learning a second language. In the meantime, they observed that certain factors pose obstacles to learning, including anxiety, shyness, and distress. One of them said:

Some students feel uneasy in the classroom and struggle to communicate with their teachers due to intense shyness, while, among other factors, a second language setting increases their stress levels.

It seems that students feel that having different traits, and asking students' opinions really determining and students would like to be more valued. Another student mentioned:

When the teacher shows a lot of positive feelings, I find myself more motivated and involved in accomplishing the learning tasks. Some of the teachers blame me when I cannot speak in English and this kind of feedback disappoint me and I become frustrated.

The important point is that teachers are in charge of establishing a warmth relationship with the students and establishing eustress or good stress for the students instead of establishing distress or bad stress for the students so that the positive emotions could help them speak more freely and becoming more efficacious. Subsequently, the researchers assessed the inter-coder reliability of the data collected from the interviews conducted with the instructors, specifically regarding their perspectives on the role of emo-sensory intelligence, L2 ego, willingness to attend class in improving learning success. After completing the coding process, the primary researcher shared the coded data with her supervisor. Subsequently, the second researcher coded the responses by identifying shared characteristics and arrived at broadly comparable findings, albeit with slight variations. The inter-coder agreement of the findings was ensured as both coders reached the same conclusion. By the recommendations proposed by Campbell et al. (2013), the researchers initially computed the ratio of coding agreements to the total number of agreements and disagreements. Eleven frequent themes were identified, with at least one researcher applying a code to each. Among these themes, seven occurrences were identified when both coders had used the same code. Hence, the inter-coder dependability would have been 63% based on the seven out of 11 calculation. Hence, the data analysis revealed seven distinct codes encompassing the common themes in the responses. These codes were categorized as follows: challenging students, ways of teaching, appreciating senses, emotional feedback, attractiveness, energy, and stress.

4. Discussion

The results of the current study are insightful and interesting. The study confirmed that there was a statistically significant association between emo-sensory intelligence, L2 ego, and willingness to attend class with students' academic achievement for EFL intermediate students. Furthermore, the results of the study revealed that the best predictor of academic achievement was willingness to attend class since this variable made the strongest contribution to explaining academic success. Finally, the commonalities emerged from the students' responses yielded seven themes.

The study found that encouraging students to attend class can increase their learning motivation. This aligns with the findings of Stewart and Joines (1987), who emphasized that paying attention to students' homework, participating in class discussions, and encouraging them to ask questions contribute to their learning development. Similar conclusions were made by Churches and Terry (2007) and Modarresi and Jalilzadeh (2020) who found that the amount of attention a teacher gives students is a key factor in their academic progress. Furthermore, interviews carried out in the research indicated that students were more inclined to cultivate a language ego that aided them in communicating successfully with their instructors. This is in line with the findings of Hsu (2009) who found that Japanese students liked foreign teachers who were more involved and cooperative than their Japanese counterparts while still expecting them to be knowledgeable and respectful. The results also support Hadley's (2003) findings that creating ample opportunities to practice language skills in the classroom and employing neuro-linguistic elements are conducive to language learning.

The study also highlighted that students with higher emo-sensory intelligence tend to feel more confident when speaking. This finding aligns with the research by Liu and Jackson (2008), which showed that students with high levels of foreign language anxiety struggle with communication, suggesting that anxiety is a strong predictor of their self-efficacy. Moreover, the literature consistently underscores the importance of creating rich learning environments (Freedman, 1993; Modarresi, 2022). Kusluvan (2003) noted that providing additional support to students can help reduce feelings of motivation. The study's findings further support previous research indicating that student motivation is closely linked to academic success (Wang & Holcombe, 2010) and that fostering motivation is an effective strategy to reduce school dropout rates (e.g. Wang & Fredricks, 2014). Increased behavioral and emotional engagement also helps reduce issues like depression, delinquency, and substance use (e.g., Li & Lerner, 2011). In line with

this, Gardner (2000) explains that motivated students are driven, persistent, and engage in activities necessary to reach their goals, showing a clear desire to succeed.

The study's findings also resonate with McCroskey's (1984) work, which found that students are more likely to feel anxious when unwilling to participate in verbal presentations. Liu and Jackson (2008) confirmed this by showing that demotivated learners are less likely to engage in communication. This highlights the role of language demotivation in students' reluctance to participate. Similarly, Croucher (2013) and Modarresi (2019) found that students who were more willing to participate in class activities were likelier to succeed in language learning.

Additionally, the study's findings are consistent with the work of Zimbardo and Boyd (1999), who found that time perspective is an individual-differences variable and positively associated with self-confidence, energy, satisfaction, and happiness. Zimbardo and Boyd (2016) also found that time perspective influences academic goals and rewards. The results of this study also align with those of Fried et al. (2016) who concluded that teachers' emotional expressions significantly impact both their cognitive processes and the emotional states of their students. Interviews with students in the current study further emphasized that when teachers gave more attention to their students, it motivated them to engage in learning. This reinforces that educational systems should aim to bridge the gap between cognition and emotion (Hosseini & Modarresi, 2015). Goleman (1995) introduced the concept of emotional illiteracy and suggested that education should bring together both the mind and the heart, a perspective that aligns with the findings of this study.

Although earlier studies faced difficulties in assessing language ego in second language education, this research elucidates how learners' mental, social, and cultural contexts underscore the intricacy of socio-psychological influences involved in language learning. Cross-cultural research has revealed that risk-taking and inhibition are key elements in language ego. This study finds that both internal factors, such as cognitive style and personality, and external factors, like the EFL environment, are significant in shaping language ego, especially within the context of Iran. The study extends the existing body of knowledge by showing how emotional factors impact students' sense of self and willingness to learn. Many classrooms in our context tend to be teacher-centered, where the teacher assumes the dominant role and there is a certain distance between the teacher and the students. However, teachers can break down these barriers by devoting more time to students, involving them in discussions, and guiding

them in their learning. This approach helps students become more engaged in the learning process and improves their abilities in both receptive and productive skills.

5. Conclusion

The findings of the study highlight the potential usefulness of students' psychological traits and perspectives of emotions, senses, and willingness with respect to learning a new language and the extent to which they have motivation to energize the class that would lead to their willingness to attend class that could promote their learning development. This study sheds new light on how emotional and neurological support from teachers in the classroom impacts student engagement and learning. Teachers' feedback goes beyond simply fostering positive emotions. It also involves encouraging class participation, providing feedback, and addressing students' academic and personal needs. As Krause (2014) and Khorsand and Modarresi (2023) point out, positive emotions contribute to enjoyment and involvement, which help create a more relaxed and supportive classroom atmosphere that enhances learning. The findings suggest that encouraging students to provide creative answers, allowing them to express themselves, and using diverse teaching techniques help boost their motivation and participation in classroom activities.

EFL learners should take advantage of their learning styles. Trying out new words and grammar structures in class and being more active in their participation can help. It is also recommended that they take some risks, and for those who are shier, writing their thoughts down and speaking them can be a good way to practice. Students should also remember to stay connected to their cultural values and identity while learning a new language. After all, traditions and customs are deeply linked to the environment they come from. For teachers, the study highlights the importance of giving students positive feedback, such as compliments and encouragement. This can engage students in problem-solving tasks and help them develop a positive attitude towards learning English. Teachers are encouraged to recognize students' contributions and create activities that allow them to express themselves, which can boost their confidence.

Although the current study includes some

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suggestions for further research, it does have some limitations. Since the sample is not a typical representation of English students at the university level, caution is warranted in generalizing the results. Moreover, the limitations of the study entail the potential bias in self-report instruments, the small sample size in the qualitative phase of the study, lack of longitudinal data, and cultural specificity of ESI in an Iranian context. Replicating this study would also be valuable in confirming its findings and understanding how effective these factors are in private English institutes settings. Lastly, further studies can investigate how emo-sensory intelligence, L2 ego, and willingness to attend class relate to other vital aspects like L2 self-efficacy and engagement.

Declarations

Competing interests

The authors state that there is no conflict of interest.

Authors' contributions

Elham Hedayati and Tahereh Zamani Behabadi took part equally in this project. All authors have read and confirmed the last edition of the manuscript.

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Ethical considerations

Ethical issues including plagiarism, consent to publication, misconduct, fabrication and/or falsification of data, double publication and/or submission, and redundancy) have been verified by all authors.

Availability of data and materials

The datasets generated during and/or analyzed during the current study are available from the corresponding author on reasonable request.

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